

LATEX IMPREGNATION FOR NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

To improve the impact resistance, natural fiber based composites are currently manufactured based on thermoplastic resins. In processes such as film stacking and LFT, composites are manufactured by melt impregnation. The main problem however is that the restricted processing temperature to prevent fiber degradation also prevents sufficient reduction of the melt viscosity. As a consequence, fiber wetting is poor, resulting in a weak fiber-matrix bond and a limited fiber volume content. According to Darcy's law, fiber impregnation should improve when the flow-path of the resin is reduced. As a solution to bring the polymer molecules in closer contact with the fibers prior to consolidation, latex impregnation is studied.

A two-phase system consisting of small thermoplastic particles in an aqueous carrier liquid is used to wet the fibers. Upon evaporation of the liquid, thermoplastic particles are deposited on the fibers and form a film. A consolidated composite is obtained upon application of heat and pressure. This paper discusses the thermodynamic processes involved such as water evaporation, particle ordering, particle deformation, film formation, annealing and consolidation and their influences on the mechanical properties of the final composite. Based on thermodynamic models and practical experiments a temperature-pressure cycle is developed for impregnation of flax non-wovens with ABS latex. To improve the results, blends of ABS latex and Vinamul latex with a lower T_g are assessed.

In general, best results with latex impregnation are obtained by drying the impregnated fibers at the Minimum Film Formation Temperature of the latex with the highest T_g (MFFT of ABS is 95 °C). Since water evaporation during drying causes ruptures in the film, an annealing step at 120 °C for 1 hour is required to restore the film, hence improving the mechanical properties of the final composite. After annealing, the laminates were consolidated in a hot platen press and cooled down under pressure. 3-Point bending tests indicate that best results are obtained with latex blends.

Key terms: latex, natural fibers, composites, film formation

INTRODUCTION

In general, one of the bottlenecks of processing thermoplastic-based composites is achieving a proper fiber impregnation given the high viscosity of the thermoplastic melt. In case of natural fibers, impregnation becomes even more difficult due to the limited process temperature required to protect the fibers from thermal degradation [1,2]. Either the viscosity of the resin remains too high and hence (i) restricts resin flow or the allowable exposure time to elevated temperatures is too short to (ii) complete resin flow. According to Darcy's law [3], fiber impregnation improves when the required flow-path of the resin is reduced; the polymer molecules should already be in close contact with the fibers before applying heat and pressure.

In latex impregnation, a two-phase system (the latex) consisting of small thermoplastic particles in an aqueous carrier liquid is used to wet the fibers. Upon extraction of the liquid phase, the thermoplastic particles are deposited as a film on the fibers, which can be consolidated into a thermoplastic-based

composite. The entire process can be divided into the following three steps, (1) Impregnation, (2) Drying and (3) Pressing. The drying step has a strong influence on the mechanical properties of the final composite as will be demonstrated in this paper. After introducing the theory of latex film formation, manufacturing and evaluation of flax based composites made by impregnation with ABS latex and latex blends are discussed.

LATEX FILM FORMATION

Latex film formation [4-11] is a process in which an aqueous dispersion of polymer particles is transformed into a continuous material. In the latex, surfactants and stabilizers keep the particles separated and deflocculated and during film formation the particles must overcome their mutual repulsion. This process has a direct influence on the morphology and mechanical properties of the final material and determines the elimination of water from the pre-preg. Film formation can be divided into three main stages: (I) evaporation of water and particle ordering, (II) particle deformation and (III) interdiffusion of polymer chains across particle-particle boundaries, see figure 1. All stages can occur simultaneously. Knowledge on each of these stages is required for proper understanding the properties of the resulting pre-pregs and consolidated composites.

Fig. 1: Water evaporation in each stage of the film formation process, (I) evaporation of water and particle ordering, (II) particle deformation and (III) interdiffusion. (Source: Joseph L. Keddie, 1997)

Stage I: Evaporation of water and particle deformation

Water can leave the latex through evaporation. The fact that the rate of evaporation is not significantly altered by the chemical compositions and particle size and is also independent of the film thickness supports the concept of a receding drying front [4]. A film cast on a flat surface will first dry on the edges due to the convex nature of the meniscus; the drying front recedes to the center of the specimen. In case of a concave meniscus the drying front recedes to the edges. When during drying the meniscus drops below the top of the particles, continued evaporation draws a flux of water from the surrounding regions (and with it particles), initiating particle ordering, see figure 2. Continuous transport of particles extends the growth of the ordered assembly around the nucleated region. The rate of evaporation strongly influences the particle ordering. Whereas slow evaporation results in dense packing, fast evaporation results in imperfections and leads to a more open packing. Temperature strongly influences the velocity of the drying front due to its effect on the evaporation rate and particle deformation and is obviously an important process parameter.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of particle assembly and ordering driven by flow to regions of faster evaporation (Source: Joseph L. Keddie, 1997)

Stage II: Particle deformation

This stage starts when the particles come to first irreversible contact, and coalescence may be observed on the latex surface. The solid content in the latex has increased up to 60 – 70 %. The overall evaporation of water is significantly reduced, allowing an orderly packing of the particles. Although a complete overview of the theory of particle deformation is beyond the scope of this paper, some terms require explanation for further reading. One is referred to literature for detailed information [12-14].

From literature it becomes clear that temperature and particle size are the most important parameters in the deformation process. Temperature influences the shear modulus and hence determines the resistance of particles against deformation. In general, with larger particle size, the allowable shear modulus still leading to sufficient deformation is higher.

When drying latex at various temperatures, a remarkable change in resulting film morphology can be found around the Minimum Film Formation Temperature (MFFT), which differs only slightly from the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymer particles. When drying above MFFT, cohesion and deformation of the particles occurs whereas below MFFT a friable discontinuous film or powder compact full of voids is obtained. A transition region can be found at temperatures slightly below MFFT. At 6 K below MFFT, a low evaporation rate can allow visco-elastic effects to form a continuous film, whereas a high evaporation rate can lead to film crazing and cracking.

Stage III: Interdiffusion of polymers chains across particle-particle boundaries

Initial formation of a continuous film marks the start of this stage. The solid content has increased up to 90 %. The remaining water leaves through interparticle channels and the soft latex becomes homogeneous and obtains mechanical properties due to chain interdiffusion. The particle boundaries become less distinct [15,16].

Interdiffusion depends on temperature and time; longer chains take longer to diffuse, but result in a higher degree of entanglement with a positive effect on the mechanical properties of not only of the deposited film, but also of the final consolidated composite. Hence, annealing at the end of the drying step to stimulate interdiffusion is an important process step. The effect of temperature is summarized in table 1.

	Higher temperature	Lower temperature
Particle packing	-	+
Particle deformation	+	-
Interdiffusion	+	-

Table 1: Effect on temperature on the 3 drying stages (+ = positive influence, - = negative influence)

In the following sections, the production process based on the abovementioned theory is explained followed by a discussion of the test results, which are in close relation to the applied production process.

Fig. 3: Consolidation conditions for ABS – Flax laminates (blue: pressure, pink: temperature)

EXPERIMENTAL

Needlepunched dew-retted flax mats were cut and stacked to form isotropic laminates and impregnated with an excess amount of ABS latex. A roller was used to squeeze out the latex to obtain the required fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 30\%$). The laminates were dried below MFFT of ABS (60 °C) at MFFT (95°C) and above MFFT (120 °C) in an air circulation oven. For drying below and at MFFT, various annealing steps were investigated. During annealing, an increase in laminate stiffness could be felt, indicating increasing interdiffusion. Final consolidation was carried out in a flat hot

platen press, according to process conditions presented in figure 3. Samples were subjected to a 3-point bending test according to ASTM D790 and examined by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

SEM ANALYSIS

Drying below MFFT and subsequent annealing

When drying below MFFT at 60 °C, a discontinuous film will result. However, due to the low evaporation rate, the resulting particle packing is dense and with an additional annealing step it should be possible to obtain a good quality film around the flax fibers. The film deposited near the fiber surface with and without annealing (1 hour at 95 °C) was examined:

Sample 1: Drying at 60 °C, no annealing

As can be seen in the SEM picture of the dried laminates in figure 4, a discontinuous film has formed around the fibers. Even after consolidation the polymer matrix remained discontinuous, see figure 5.

Fig. 4: Particle coalescence after drying (60 °C)

Fig. 5: Particle coalescence after consolidation

Sample 2: Drying at 60 °C, annealing at 95 °C for 1 hour

The coherence in the polymer matrix has increased after drying (figure 6) and after consolidation (figure 7) compared to sample 1.

Fig. 6: Particle coalescence after drying (60 °C) and annealing (95 °C)

Fig. 7: Particle coalescence consolidation

Drying at MFFT and subsequent annealing

Compared to drying below MFFT the water evaporation rate will increase when drying at MFFT (90 °C), leaving a less dense particle packing. The higher temperature however promotes particle

deformation and further improvements are expected with additional annealing. Again samples with and without annealing (1 hour at 120 °C) were examined.

Sample 3: Drying at 95 °C, no annealing

The SEM picture in figure 8 shows that although particle boundaries are still visual, the particles are more deformed compared to drying below MFFT. Still no continuous film is obtained after consolidation, see figure 9.

Fig. 8: Particle coalescence after drying (95 °C)

Fig. 9: Particle coalescence after consolidation

Sample 4: Drying at 95 °C, annealing at 120 °C for 1 hour

Annealing has resulted in a void free continuous film as can be seen in figure 10. Also the consolidated composite shows a continuous matrix, see figure 11.

Fig. 10: Particle coalescence after drying (95 °C) and annealing (120 °C)

Fig. 11: Particle coalescence after consolidation

Drying above MFFT

Drying the laminates above MFFT (120 °C, sample 5) was not followed by an annealing step. Although the SEM pictures indicate particle deformation and formation of a continuous film around the fibers, see figure 12, it is to be expected that the particles are not nicely packed due to vigorous evaporation of the water. This will become clear from the results of the 3-point bending test.

Fig. 12: Particle coalescence after drying (120 °C)

MECHANICAL TESTING

The following results were obtained with a 3-point bending test according to ASTM D790, see table 2.

Sample	Temperature	Annealing	Flexural modulus (Gpa)	Flexural strength (Mpa)
1	Below MFFT (60 °C)	No	3.3	60
2	Below MFFT (60 °C)	1 hour, 95 °C	4.9	71
3	At MFFT (95 °C)	No	3.5	67
4	At MFFT (95 °C)	1 hour, 120 °C	5.9	85
5	Above MFFT (120 °C)	No	3.5	70

Table 2: Mechanical properties of consolidated ABS – Flax laminates with various drying conditions (3-point bending test according to ASTM D790)

Although particle deformation leads to a continuous film when drying at MFFT followed by annealing, cracks still appear in the middle of these films between the fibers, as can be seen on the SEM picture in figure 13. Similar results can be found for the other drying conditions. In the next section the application of blends of latex to reduce the cracks is investigated.

Fig. 13: SEM picture of the cracks in the middle of the film between the fibers.

LATEX BLENDS

Given the cracks shown in figure 13, it was not possible with these process conditions to completely deform and coalesce the latex particles into a unified continuous matrix. In this section blends of ABS latex with latices with a lower T_g and smaller particle size are investigated for reducing the cracks. The hard ABS particles deform to provide strength to the film, whereas the softer latex particles (Vinamul, see table 3) fill in the cracks, without the need for annealing. To investigate the effect of blending in the first two stages of film formation, all blends (80 % ABS latex) were dried at the MFFT of ABS (95 °C) for 1 hour and consolidated without additional annealing step.

Latex	T_g [°C]	Polymer type
Vinacryl 7179	50	X-Link Styrene-Acrylic polymer
Vinamul 3525	60	X-Link Vinyl-Chloride acetate-Ethylene terpolymer
Vinacryl 4373	55	X-Link Acrylic polymer

Table 3: Vinamul latices.

Consolidation conditions for the ABS-Vinamul blends are given in figure 14. The results of the 3-point bending test are given in table 4.

Processing Conditions for ABS-Vinamul Blends

Fig. 14: Consolidation conditions for ABS/Vinamul – Flax laminates (blue: pressure, pink: temperature)

Latex	Flexural modulus [Gpa]	Flexural strength [Mpa]
ABS	3.5	67.3
ABS + 7179	5.9	76.6
ABS + 3525	6.1	63.2
ABS + 4373	5.7	80.3

Table 4: Mechanical properties of consolidated ABS/Vinamul – Flax laminates (3-point bending test according to ASTM D790)

As can be seen, mechanical properties improve by blending the ABS latex with Vinamul latex. SEM observations still clearly indicate the ABS particle boundaries in the film, showing no improvements compared to the neat ABS impregnated laminates, see figure 15. The effect of blending on crack closure is however significant, see figure 16. Still, further improvements are expected by optimizing the drying cycle and by adding an annealing step.

Fig. 15: Particle coalescence after drying (100 °C), left: ABS + 7179, center: ABS + 3525, right: ABS + 4373

Fig. 16: Resulting crack-closure of the film between the fibers due to blending the ABS latex with Vinamul 7179.

CONCLUSIONS

In latex impregnation, a two-phase system (the latex) consisting of small thermoplastic particles in an aqueous carrier liquid is used to wet the fibers. Upon water evaporation, the particles are deposited as a film around and in between the fibers. The flow path length of the thermoplastic resin during consolidation is significantly reduced, hence reducing the problem of natural fiber degradation in this processing step.

It was shown that the quality of the deposited film has a strong influence on the mechanical properties of the consolidated composite. There are three main stages that occur during film formation: (I) evaporation of water and particle ordering, (II) particle deformation and (III) interdiffusion of polymer chains across particle-particle boundaries. Temperature plays a major role in each stage, especially the Minimum Film Formation Temperature (MFFT). Drying below MFFT results into dense particle packing but in less particle deformation, whereas above MFFT the opposite occurs. For ABS – flax composites, best results were obtained when drying at MFFT of ABS (95 °C), followed by an annealing step (120 °C) to promote interdiffusion. At 30 % fiber volume content, a flexural modulus was obtained of 5.9 GPa and flexural strength of 85 MPa. However, still cracks appeared in the deposited film prior to consolidation. Investigation on the effect of blending the ABS latex with 20 % latex with lower T_g (Vinamul) on the first two stages of the film formation process showed crack closure and improvement in mechanical properties. Further improvements are expected by optimizing the drying cycle for blends and by adding an annealing step.

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